

A Study of Perceived Stress, Anxiety, Depression and Coping Strategies in Wives of Patients with Alcohol Dependence

Krupa Mukeshbhai Unadkat¹, Bharat Navinchandra Panchal², Ashokkumar Ukabhai Vala³, Sneha Bhagvanbhai Vadher⁴, Dimple Ramankumar Gupta⁵, Chirag Sanjaybhai Ambaliya⁶

¹Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Bhavnagar, Gujarat, India

²Retired Professor and Head, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Bhavnagar, Gujarat, India

³Professor and Head, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Bhavnagar, Gujarat, India

⁴Consultant Psychiatrist at Government Hospital, Daman

⁵Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Hamdard Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, New Delhi

⁶Senior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Government Medical College, Bhavnagar, Gujarat, India

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Corresponding author: Dr Krupa Mukeshbhai Unadkat

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Abstract

Background: Alcohol use disorder is quite prevalent in general population. Often the family members of alcoholics suffer intense psychological, physical and social trauma due to the core drinking problem of the family member. Most deeply affected are the wives of alcoholics. To deal with such situations the wives use coping strategies which are combined efforts of behavioral and psychological changes to reduce the stress related to their spouses drinking.

Objectives: To study assess the prevalence of perceived stress, anxiety, depression assess coping strategies in wives of patients with alcohol dependence.

Material and Methods: This was an observational, cross sectional, single-centered, interview based study of total 150 consecutive female aged 20-80 years whose Husbands were admitted in psychiatry ward & coming to psychiatry OPD of Sir.T.Hospital, Bhavnagar. Interview of their Husbands was taken for diagnosis of Alcohol Use Disorder using DSM- 5(Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5) Criteria. Every subject was assessed by proforma containing demographic details, Cohen Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10), Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A), Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HRDS), Coping Inventory For Stressful Situations (CISS-21) And their Husbands' Severity of Alcohol is Assessed By using questionnaires of SAD-Q (Severity of Alcohol Dependence).

Results: Frequency of mild, moderate, severe and very severe depression is 18.67%, 14%, 10% and 8.67% depression respectively in wives of alcohol dependent males. There is significant association between emotion oriented coping and duration alcohol. There is no significant association between any coping behaviors and duration of marriage. There is significant association between task, emotion and avoidance oriented coping and education. There is

significant association between task, emotion and avoidance oriented coping and anxiety, depression and perceived stress.

Conclusion: Wives of alcohol dependent male patients are having high level of perceived stress, anxiety and depression. The most common mechanism of coping used is avoidance oriented coping in wives of alcohol dependent males. Duration of marriage is not having any correlation with coping mechanism. Education and socioeconomical class are having correlation with coping in wives of alcohol dependent male patients.

Keywords: Alcohol Use disorder, Wives, Perceived Stress, Anxiety, Depression, Coping.

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Introduction

International Classification of Disease, 10th edition (ICD-10) describes alcohol dependence syndrome as cluster of behavior, cognition and physiological phenomena that is seen after repeated use of alcohol substance and one develops a strong desire to consume the drug and has difficulty in controlling the behavior to take the substance in spite of knowing its harmful consequences, a significant importance is given to alcohol use rather than other activities, their tolerance increases, and withdrawal features in form of physical symptoms are seen [1].

A need for daily use of large amount of alcohol for adequate functioning, a regular pattern of Heavy drinking limited to weekends, and long periods of sobriety interspersed with binges of heavy alcohol lasting for weeks or months strongly suggest alcohol dependence and alcohol abuse. In addition patients of alcohol dependence and alcohol abuse show impaired social or occupational functioning because of alcohol use, legal difficulties, and arguments or difficulties with family members or friends about excessive alcohol consumption [2].

The consequences of alcohol consumption and stressful life events may trigger psychological, biological, behavioral responses, which markedly diminishes the Individual's ability to respond or react to emotional distress thereby increasing the likelihood of psychological problems [3].

Anxiety disorders are associated with significant morbidities and often are chronic and resistant to treatment. A fascinating aspect of Anxiety disorder is exquisite interplay of genetic and experiential factors. Little doubt exists that abnormal genes predispose to pathological anxiety states; however, evidence clearly indicates that traumatic life events and stress are also etiologically important [2].

A Depressed mood and loss of interest or pleasure are the key symptoms of depression. Patient often describes the symptom of depression as one of agonizing emotional pain and sometimes complaint about being unable to cry. About two-third of all depressed patients contemplate suicide, and 10 to 15 % commit suicide. Almost all depressed patients complaint about reduced energy, They have difficulty finishing tasks, are impaired at school or work, and have less motivation to undertake new projects [2].

It is often said and known that the life of the family members living with an alcoholic person is challenging in every aspect of their lives. Alcoholism affects not only the one who consumes but also those who fall within his surrounding area [4,5].

Women whose partners have alcohol problems are more exposed to victimization, injury, mood disorders, anxiety disorders, and being in fair or poor health. The odds ratio is also significantly higher in these women than in

spouses whose men were not alcohol dependent [6].

Co-dependency is definite term used for wives of alcoholics, especially important in creating and maintaining symptoms of the alcoholic husband. It is also attributed as primary disease in spouses of alcoholics [8].

The strategies chosen depend both upon situational and individual factors: the coping resources. Coping has been defined as "continuously changing behavioral or cognitive efforts to meet inner and/or outer demands which compel subjective limits of the person or exceed his/her self-resources [10]. Whether a coping strategy is effective or not is directly dependent on numerous factors such as how one perceives the stressor, are enough coping strategies available and how is the outcome of that very coping strategy used [11].

This study will help in early diagnosis of perceived stress, anxiety and depression in wives of men with alcohol dependence and that will improve the outcome of patients with alcohol dependence as spouses are the core family member in treatment of alcohol dependence in men. Present study was done with an aim to assess the prevalence of Perceived Stress, Anxiety, Depression and Coping Strategies in Wives of Patients with Alcohol Dependence.

Material and Methods

We carried out a cross sectional, observational, single centre, interview based study of total 150 consecutive female aged 18-65 years whose husbands are admitted in psychiatry ward or coming to psychiatry OPD of Sir.T.Hospital, Bhavnagar . Prior approval from local ethics committee (Institutional Review Board) was taken. Written informed consent from every participant was taken after explaining the purpose of the study. Anonymity and confidentiality of participants were maintained. Interview was taken in participant's vernacular language (Gujarati) or Hindi or English. Those participants who gave

consent & were married for more than 1 year & whose husband's SAD-Q score is more than 16 were included in the study. Those patients having past history of co-morbid psychiatric disorders: schizophrenia & other psychotic disorder, Substance use disorder other than tobacco were excluded from the study.

Every participant's responses were recorded in a proforma containing details of demographic variables such as participant's initials, age, religion, residence, occupation, gross family income, Duration of Marriage, education, duration of marriage & Husband's SAD-Q score.

Interview of every participant's husband was taken for diagnosis of Alcohol Use Disorder using DSM 5(Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5) Criteria[41]. Spouses of Patients whose score is more than 16 were included in the study. Cohen Perceived Stress Scale(PSS)-10 Questions is the most widely used psychological instrument for measuring the perception of stress.[43] The Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression (HRSD) Also called the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS), abbreviated HAM-D, is a multiple-item questionnaire used to provide an indication of depression, and as a guide to evaluate recovery.[44] The Hamilton Anxiety rating scale was one of the first rating scales developed to measure the severity of anxiety symptoms, and is still widely used today in both clinical and research settings.[45] The coping inventory in stressful situation-21 (CISS-21) has been developed to assess three coping strategies: task-oriented, emotion-oriented and avoidance coping having 7 questions for each, total 21 questions.[46]

Statistical Analysis

The recorded data was compiled and entered in a spreadsheet computer program (Microsoft Excel 2007) and then exported to data editor page of SPSS version 15 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). For all tests, confidence level and level of significance were set at 95% and 5% respectively.

Results

The study was carried out at Psychiatry department, Sir. T. Hospital, Bhavnagar to find out the prevalence of Perceived Stress,

Anxiety, Depression and Coping Strategies in Wives of Patients with Alcohol Dependence. Total 150 wives of Alcohol Dependent male patients are included in the study.

Table 1: Demographic Variables of Participants

Variables		No	Frequency (%)
Age (Years)	20-35	74	49.33%
	36-50	63	42%
	51-65	12	8%
	66-80	1	0.67%
Religion	Hindu	147	98%
	Muslim	3	2%
Resident	Rural	44	29.33%
	Urban	55	36.67%
	Town	51	34%
Occupation	Unemployed	66	44%
	Labour	82	54.67%
	Semi-profession	2	1.33%
Education	Illiterate	72	48%
	Primary	65	43.33%

Data is represented in percentage and Mean \pm S.D. Mean Duration of Marriage is 16.13 years.n Socioeconomical Class was determined according to Modified BG Prasad Socio-economical Classification. Mean Duration of Alcohol dependence is 16.58 years.

Table 2: Frequency of Anxiety Participants (wives of alcohol dependent patients)

Variable	No. and Frequency (%)			
	None HAM-A <7	Mild HAM-A 8-14	Moderate HAM-A 15-23	Severe HAM-A \geq 24
Anxiety	70 (46.67%)	14 (9.33%)	46 (30.67%)	20 (13.33%)

Table 2 shows Frequency of anxiety in wives of alcohol dependent patients which was Mild, Moderate and Severe 9.33%, 30.67%, 30.67% Respectively and No anxiety in 46.67%.

Table 3: Frequency of Depression in Participants

Variable	No. and Frequency (%)				
	None HRDS 0-7	Mild HRDS 8-13	Moderate HRDS 14-18	Severe HRDS 19-22	Very Severe HRDS \geq 23
Depression	73 (48.67%)	28 (18.67%)	21 (14%)	16 (10%)	13(8.67%)

Table 3 shows Frequency of Depression in wives of alcohol dependent patients which is Mild, Moderate and severe and Very Severe 18.67%, 14%, 10% and 8.67% respectively and No Depression in 48.67%.

Table 4: Distribution of Participants according to (coping inventory for stressful situations class-21)

CISS-21 Score	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean	S.D.	C.V.
Task-oriented	7	35	25.37	11.45	0.45
Emotion-oriented	7	35	21.32	8.43	0.39
Avoidance-oriented	7	35	21.78	7.79	0.35
Total Score	46	90	68.48	10.53	0.15

Table no. 4 gives the distribution of Wives as per CISS-21 scoring. CISS avoidance had mean score of 21.78 with SD of 7.79, while CISS task had mean score of 25.37 with SD of 11.45 and CISS Emotion had mean score of 21.32 with SD of 8.43. The mean CISS total score is 68.48 with SD of 10.53.

Table 5: Association of Duration of Alcohol Dependence with Perceived Stress, Anxiety and Depression of Wives of Alcohol Dependent Patients

Duration of Alcohol Dependence (years)	Perceived stress (PSS-10) (No.)			Anxiety (HAMA) (No.)				Depression (HRDS) (No.)				
	low	Moderate	High	none	mild	moderate	severe	none	mild	moderate	severe	Very severe
1-20	42	8	63	47	11	41	14	50	19	19	14	11
21-40	19	2	13	20	3	5	6	20	9	2	1	2
41-60	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0
P value	0.0954			0.1381				0.2201				

Table 5 shows that there is no significant association between Duration Of Alcohol dependence with Perceived Stress, Anxiety And Depression Wives Of Alcohol Dependent Patients.

Table 6: Association of Duration of Marriage with Perceived Stress, Anxiety and Depression of Wives of Alcohol Dependent Patients

Duration of marriage (years)	Perceived stress (PSS-10) (No.)			Anxiety (HAM-A) (No.)				Depression (HRDS) (No.)				
	low	Moderate	High	none	mild	moderate	severe	none	mild	moderate	severe	Very severe
1-20	38	6	57	38	13	35	15	41	23	15	13	9
21-40	25	4	19	31	1	11	5	31	5	6	2	4
41-60	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
P value	0.2822			0.0573				0.2528				

Table 6 shows that there is significant association between Duration Of Marriage and Anxiety but there is no significant association between Duration of Marriage with Depression and Perceived Stress in Wives Of Alcohol Dependent Patients.

Table 7: Association of husband's duration of Alcohol Dependence, duration of marriage, severity of alcohol dependence, age, occupation, education, socioeconomical status, perceived stress, anxiety and depression With Coping of Wives of Alcohol Dependent Patients

Variables	CISS-21		
	Task oriented coping	Emotion oriented coping	Avoidance oriented coping
Husband's duration of alcohol dependence	0.3151	0.3176	0.0028
Duration of marriages	0.4849	0.2421	0.5044
Husband's severity of alcohol dependence (SAD-Q)	0.0207	0.0374	0.0832
Age	0.8563	0.2662	0.0059
Occupation	0.0000	0.0000	0.3955
Education	0.0000	0.0046	0.0056
Socioeconomical status	0.0139	0.0164	0.0004
Perceived stress(PSS-10)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Anxiety(HAM-A)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Depression(HRDS)	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Table 7 shows there is significant association between husband's duration of alcohol with avoidance oriented coping, no association of duration of marriage with any three of coping, there is significant association between husband's severity of alcohol with task and emotion oriented coping, there is significant association between age and avoidance oriented coping, there is significant association between occupation with task and emotion oriented coping, there is significant association between education and all three type of coping.

There is significant association between socioeconomical status with all three type of coping, there is significant association between perceived stress with all three type of coping, there is significant association between anxiety with all three type of coping, there is significant association between depression with all three type of coping.

Discussion

We conducted a study to find out the prevalence of Perceived Stress, Anxiety, Depression and Coping Strategies in Wives of Patients with Alcohol Dependence. We conducted a study to find out the prevalence of

Perceived Stress, Anxiety, Depression and Coping Strategies in Wives of Patients with Alcohol Dependence. Our study shows that there is 51.33% frequency of Depression in wives of alcohol dependent male patients in which 18.67%, 14%, 10% and 8.67% is mild, moderate, severe and very severe respectively. It is consistent with the previous studies where wives of alcohol dependent male patients are having high level of Depression [12-14].

In this study shows that there is there is 53.33% frequency of Anxiety in wives of alcohol dependent male patients in which 9.33%, 30.67% and 13.33% is mild, moderate, severe and respectively. It is consistent with the previous study where wives of alcohol dependent male patients are having high level of Anxiety [13].

In present study shows that there is there is 42.67%, 6.67% and 50.67% of low, moderate and High level Of Perceived Stress, respectively in wives of alcohol dependent male patients. It is consistent with the previous studies which showed that there is more psychiatric treatments during marriage years of the wives of alcoholics can be interpreted in

accordance with the "stressed wife" theory [14,15].

In this study shows that the most common coping mechanism used by wives of alcohol dependent male patients is Avoidance Oriented Coping. It is consistent with the previous studies which shows that commonest coping used by wives of Alcohol Dependent males is Avoidance, discord, indulgence and fearful withdrawal [14,17]. Our study shows that there is significant association between Avoidance Oriented Coping and duration alcohol dependence. In previous study there is no association found between any Coping Behaviors and duration of Alcohol dependence [17] Our study shows that there is no significant association between any coping behaviors and duration of marriage. It is consistent with the findings of previous study which shows no significant correlation between the coping behaviours and duration of marriage.

Our study shows that there is significant association between severity of alcohol and Task and Emotion oriented coping but no significant association was found between severity of alcohol and Avoidance oriented coping. Our study shows that there is significant association between age and Avoidance oriented coping but no significant association between age and Task and Emotion oriented coping. Our study shows that there is significant association between Task and Emotion Oriented Coping and Occupation. In previous study there is no association found between any Coping Behaviors and Occupation [17]

Our study shows there is significant association between Severity of alcohol and perceived stress and depression but there is no significant association between severity of alcohol and Anxiety.

In our study there is significant association of task, emotion and avoidance oriented coping with perceived stress, anxiety and depression so it is concluded that there is no relation of

using any type coping mechanism by wives of alcohol dependent male and having perceived stress, anxiety and depression in them.

Our study has certain limitations like

Being a cross sectional study, cause-effect relationship can't be established with this study. Small sample size, Recruiting participants from single centre i.e. Sir.T.Hospital, Bhavnagar. Further large sample sized and multi-centric cohort studies are recommended to have further insight in this subject.

Conclusion

The most common mechanism of coping used is Avoidance oriented Coping in wives of Alcohol Dependent Males as assessed by Coping Inventory in stressful situation-21. As there is significant association of avoidance with duration of alcohol dependence, it is concluded that duration of alcohol is more if wives of those patients uses avoidance coping. So it is better to avoid avoidance coping type of mechanism to cut the duration of alcohol dependence in their husbands. As there is significant association of task, emotion and avoidance oriented coping with perceived stress, anxiety and depression so it is concluded that there is no relation of using any type coping mechanism by wives of alcohol dependent male and having perceived stress, anxiety and depression in them. As there is high frequency of Perceived stress, anxiety and Depression is found in wives of Alcohol Dependent patients; screening of spouses of alcohol dependent patients should be done and management of them should be done by pharmacological or non- pharmacological therapies.

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